

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE GROWTH CHARACTERISTICS OF *JUNIPERUS COMMUNIS* L. IN DEPENDENCE ON LIGHT INTENSITY IN TURIANCHAI STATE RESERVE (AZERBAIJAN)

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Abstract

The juniper plant is the main component of arid sparse forests in Azerbaijan. These forests have a dual character. Some of the plant groupings in the area depend on the important informational features of the tree layer, while others are plant associations that do not rely on the tree layer. Another important feature of the plant communities formed by the juniper plant is the low coverage of crowns (not less than 0.3). However, this indicator is not stable and depends on factors such as the type of plant, the stage of succession, and the biological age of the plant. The incomplete mutual covering of canopies has an aging effect on forming plant communities of the lower layers and the living environment. In general, the degree of mutual coverage of canopies in plant communities differs sharply from each other in the forest and sparse forest strip.

Keywords: juniperus communis l, light, Azerbaijan.

Juniper plant is not demanding on environmental factors. Their morphological characteristics have led to environmental tolerance. Juniper, which grows naturally in stony rocky areas in the high mountain belt, is constantly exposed to high temperatures.

Light also plays a very important role in the development of a juniper plant, so a mature juniper tree is a heliophyte and develops under 100% light conditions.

Juvenile juniper trees are known for their ability to thrive in shaded areas. In 2019, 2020, and 2022, we monitored the growth and development of *Juniperus communis* L. in Turyanchay State Nature Reserve under different lighting conditions. The results were analyzed using the MS Excel program, and the impact of light intensity on plant development was mathematically assessed. The level of illumination in the environment was measured using a KOOSR TASI 8721 luxmeter

Table 1

Effect of light intensity on branch growth of *Juniperus communis* L.

Branches	Annual growth (m)		
	2019	2020	2022
In unshaded area (Sunlight maximum) (12000 lx)			
1	0.02	0.04	0.06
2	0.08	0.03	0.05
3	0.06	0.06	0.01
4	0.05	0.06	0.04
5	0.06	No information	0.03
6	0.01	0.06	0.04
7	0.01	0.05	0.02
8	0.07	0.08	No information
9	0.05	0.04	0.05
10	0.02	0.05	0.02
In shaded area (Sunlight medium) (500-700)			
1	0.04	0.02	0.05
2	0.05	0.00	0.06
3	0.08	0.02	0.04
4	0.05	0.04	0.05
5	0.02	0.03	0.05
6	0.03	0.02	0.03
7	0.02	0.03	0.02
8	0.02	0.01	No information
9	0.02	0.05	0.01
10	0.04	0.06	0.02

Table 1 shows the dynamics of branch elongation in light and shade zones. The Pearson correlation coefficient between the level of environmental illumination and the growth dynamics of branches was determined as 0.53. This shows that there is a weak positive correlation between light and growth. The juniper plant is common in arid environments, and soils in this environment are high in Ca. Adding calcium to the soil reduces the harmful effects of hydrogen and aluminum ions and improves the structure of the soil. Calcium carbonate neutralizes the acids in the soil and creates weak alkalinity. As a calciphile plant, junipers absorb more calcium than other plants.

The soils of the areas where arid sparse forests are widespread in Azerbaijan are rich in calcium and calcium-containing compounds, which in turn indicates that the erosion products of the Cretaceous and Paleogene periods are also involved in the formation of the soil cover of the mentioned areas. The soil layer formed as a result of erosion is often composed of large-sized alluvial elements. Carbonate - the water regime in which mountain forest soils develop is usually of a non-washing type. The main feature of the mentioned soils is the high content of calcium carbonates. Carbonate compounds begin to be noted from the upper layers, and starting from the B horizon, the amount of carbonates increases sharply (CaCO₃ 36-48%). In the lower horizons, the amount of carbonates increases and can sometimes even reach 70%. Due to the high content of carbonates, the upper layers of these soils are alkaline, neutral, and sometimes weakly acidic, and the lower layers are usually alkaline. This diversity of pH in the upper and lower layers of the soil is due to the leaching process and the acid environment-creating effect of the forest floor, and the alkaline reaction in the lower layers is due to the abundance of carbonates. Junipers are lithophytic plants in relation to the physical properties of the soil and grow better in stony rocky areas.

References

1. Gurbanov, E.M. , Mamedova, Z.C. & Rzaeva, A.A. *Juniperus polycarpus* K. Koch (Turkestan Juniper) Species in Turianchai Preserve (Azerbaijan Republic) 2017. *Journal of Food Science and Engineering* pages 458-60
2. Gurbanov, E. & Rzaeva, AA. Biomorphological Analysis and Identification of Subspecies of *Juniperus communis* in Azerbaijan. *Asian Journal of Plant Science and Research*, 2017 , 7(3) page 14-16
3. Gurbanov, E.M. & Rzaeva, A.A. Comparative analysis of *Juniperus communis* L. (Cupressaceae) berry oils in Azerbaijan. *International Conference "Chemical Science and Education, Problems and Prospects of Development"*, Dedicated to the International Year of the Periodic Table of Chemical Elements. Makhachkala, 2019 , pages 150-153
4. Huseynova, H.Z. New distribution areas of some species of plants on the southern part of the Caspian coast. *Biosystems diversity Oles Honchar Dnipro National University Ukraine* 2023 31 (1) p 123-130
5. Huseynova, H.Z. Vegetation of the southern part of the Caspian coast and its nutritional value. *Biosystems diversity Oles Honchar Dnipro National University Ukraine* 2022 31 (3) p 205-212
6. Mammadova, Z. J. Seed Productivity of Some Leguminous Plants Studied at the Level of Cenopopulation in Azerbaijan, *Bulletin Of Science and Practice* 2020, № 6 pages 58-65
7. Rzayeva, A.A. Seed propagation of *Juniperus foetidissima* Willd. in Absheron. *Bulletin Of Science and Practice* 2021. № 1 pages 55-58
8. Rzayeva, A. Адаптации листьев *Juniperus rufescens* Link. в горах Южного Кавказа (Азербайджан). *Bulletin of Science and Practice* 6 (10)